
EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN THE FORMATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE'S WORLD VIEW IN FOLK PEDAGOGY

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Annotation.

In our country, physically healthy, spiritually mature, harmonious and well-developed young people in all aspects, independent thinkers, intellectual potential, deep knowledge and modern outlook, capable of taking responsibility for the fate and future of our country. The responsibility of consistently continuing the task of bringing up the generation to adulthood is, first of all, the responsibility of the family.

Key words.

spiritual and spiritual, respect, love, duty, conscience, honesty, friendship, companionship, neighborliness.

Looking at the birth of a mentally and spiritually healthy child as the result of the work of a healthy and harmonious family, it is the duty of each of us to create an environment of mutual respect and love, high moral and spiritual values in the family. National and universal values play a very important role in fulfilling this task. Values are the basis of the development of society, a powerful factor that transfers the successes achieved in the historical development of the nation from generation to generation. Looking at the stages of historical development, every society and state did not develop without developing and strengthening its national values.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired the video selector meeting held on January 19, 2021 on the issues of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work and strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard: "If society if the body of his life is economy, his soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values," they acknowledged. So what is

value itself? Values mean all the things that are important for people and humanity. We interpret the essence of values by fully conveying, teaching, and educating the traditions of people's historical experience to future generations. Therefore, it is an urgent matter to respect, honor, sincerely fulfill national spiritual values and keep them in their original form, and at the same time, to harmonize universal human values in the family environment. Values are divided into different types and cover all aspects of life. In particular, a person and his life are the highest value. There is no need to talk about the value of something where there are no people. That is why honoring the dignity of a person, improving his life, developing his knowledge and cultural level, maintaining his health, and protecting his life are the main directions of our state's policy. It is necessary to develop a sense of seeing and feeling the subtle and elegant beauties of nature. A person's idea of what nationality he belongs to is not only an idea, but also a feeling. National consciousness in a person Marufova Gulnora Makhmudovna, First Deputy Minister of Community and Family Support, Collection of materials of the republican scientific-practical conference on "Issues of formation of national and universal values in the modern family and child upbringing" 5 and pride otherwise, it is difficult to imagine that he will understand the national values of the nation, if he does not feel that he belongs to it. □ To form moral values in the minds of our children: to expand concepts and ideas of respect and love for the Motherland, parents, past generations; creating ideas about duty, conscience, honesty, responsibility; expanding ideas about friendship, companionship, neighborly relations is the first task that needs to be solved. Aesthetic values are to educate the aesthetic sense and perception of our children, to form their external and internal beauty. In order to form aesthetic values in them: forming in the child's mind the feeling of preservation of practical, architectural, musical and artistic works, as well as holidays of various nature, which have come down to us from our ancestors; to appreciate beauty, to be able to distinguish real beauty from fake beauty;

At the same time, we are all realizing another truth, that is, only a truly enlightened person can understand the value of a person, the values of the nation, in a word, his identity, live in a free and liberated society, and participate in the world community of our independent country. He can fight selflessly to take a dignified place he deserves. Our people, who have breathed from a spiritual and spiritual climate since ancient times, especially in today's responsible era, at a time when intelligence, intelligence and courage, worldly potential and national pride are required, should be even closer and more loving. is demanding. Universal

human values are deeper and broader than national values in terms of content and gain universal importance. Universal values correspond to the goals and aspirations of all nations, peoples and peoples of the world. The set of universal human values includes universal problems related to the development of human civilization. The most important of them are the development of science on earth, maintaining peace, ensuring international security, preventing various diseases, protecting nature, ending poverty and illiteracy, providing industrial raw materials, energy sources and food, space and issues such as exploitation of the world's ocean resources, preservation and transmission to the next generation of rare works of art, folk art, architecture and music of world importance. Artistic, architectural and spiritual works created by our ancestors are more valuable wealth than any jewelry. These riches have served him for centuries. When the Athenian democracy was in crisis before our era, Greek philosophers raised the question of value. For the first time in the history of socio-political and legal thinking, they showed that "man is the highest value", and advocated measuring all aspects of the world with the "criterion of humanity".

The great thinker Socrates answered the question, "What is value?" as "every person's self-awareness." The family, which is the place of formation of values, and the value system characteristic of it, determine the future of society. It is our national characteristic to care about the future generation, to strive to raise a healthy, mature generation. Every person living in this holy land struggles and works throughout his life to see the happiness and perfection of his children. The family is a center of education that ensures the eternity of life, continuity of generations, polishes our sacred traditions, and, at the same time, directly affects the future generations. Family traditions, values, and customs form a child's personality. Chapter XIV of the Constitution of our independent republic is dedicated to the family, and includes full and reasonable legal protection of all issues related to the Uzbek family and relationships. Since the formation of the Uzbek family, issues such as equal rights of the parties, free consent in marriage, support and upbringing of children by parents, care of their parents by children have been expressed in the constitution. We can proudly point out that Article 66 of Chapter XIV of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: "Adult, able-bodied children are obliged to take care of their parents." is the reflection of our national value in the law. One of the unique features of the Uzbek family is the high position and rank of elderly people in the family - grandparents, they are always honored, they are consulted on all issues, and it is followed to start work. The

purpose of recognizing these characteristic features of the Uzbek family is that only then will the unique aspects of "family education" be fully revealed.

In the process of education, there will be an opportunity to think more clearly about the place, weight and importance of the national-cultural heritage. Let's take, for example, the high position of the husband in the family, the fact that the woman has her rights, and that children respect their parents. These values, which have been instilled in the hearts of our ancestors for many years, need to be further refined today. Especially in today's rapidly changing age, absurd influences are increasing, and they have a negative effect on the life of people and society. The consequences are becoming more and more unprecedented. At this time, the role of the family in society is very important. The soil of the motherland begins with the family. Parents should be able to notice some unpleasant things that negatively affect the moral image of our children. If we create the necessary conditions in the family for children to use family news media, press, news of scientific conferences, fiction literature, the atmosphere in the family will improve even more. In our opinion, the role of national family values is increasing more than ever in the current conditions in which New Uzbekistan is being established. In short, national and universal values are a powerful factor for the development of society and its foundation, which conveys the successes achieved in the historical development of the nation from generation to generation. Therefore, let's be a beacon that shows our children the right path so that they can pass through the important passage in the family as they go through childhood, adolescence, and adulthood.

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